

Identification of management zones based on soil and yield in slope citrus field

Kengo Usui ^{*1, 2}, Sakae Shibusawa ², Hiroki Umeda ³, Masakazu Kodaira ², Qichen Li ²

1 Forestry and Forest Products Research Institute, Ibaraki, Japan

2 Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Tokyo, Japan

3 NARO Institute of Vegetable and Floriculture Science, Ibaraki, Japan

Abstract

This paper aims to 1) describe the spatial variation of soil parameters and yield in a steep slope citrus field and 2) identify the management zones based on the variation of soil properties and yield from the point of view of a row-based irrigation system. The test field was located on Iwagi Island, Ehime Prefecture. Soil volumetric water content (VMC) and electrical conductivity (EC) were collected from 51 locations at 3 different depths: the ground surface, 20 cm depth, and 40 cm depth. The yield data of 89 trees between 2010 and 2013 were also collected. Yield, VMC, EC, elevation and combination of yield and soil parameters were classified by cluster analysis with the fuzzy c-means method. The cluster analysis divided, VMC into 3 groups, EC into 3 or 4 groups, yield into 5 groups, elevation into 3 groups and combination of yield and soil parameters into 2 groups. The classified groups clearly showed the influence of cultivation of each variable. Comparing the row irrigation system with the cluster analysis results, row irrigation affected the yield and soil parameters. Some clustered groups in the same irrigation row were also observed. It is suggested that the existing row irrigation system can adjust the variability of the field yield.

Background

Citrus is the most popular fruits in Japan. However, as abnormal weather such as drought and long rain occurs frequently, development of technology capable of producing fruits of stable quality even under such conditions has been demanded. As an example of a technology that can cope with this, the drip irrigation and liquid fertilization method with year-round plastic mulching (Marudori in Japanese) was developed that covers the park with multi-seats throughout the year and combines with drip irrigation equipment (Morinaga et al., 2004). Marudori method is low water consumption and high water use efficiency since the irrigation amount can be controlled automatically by a solenoid valve.

The current Marudori method is a system that simultaneously controls irrigation and fertilization within a garden or block unit, development of a tree-based management method that realizes uniformity of quality by reducing variations within the park as much as possible is required (Morinaga et al., 2010). In addition, there is a report that variability of yield exists in the field (Molin et al., 2012; Zaman and Schumann, 2006), it is necessary to try not only quality but also uniformity of yield of each tree.

There is precision agriculture as a management strategy to minimize dispersion within the park as much as possible. Based on this idea of variable rate technologies, management zones have become widespread as their important method. This method clarifies spaces with similar characteristics and manages them uniformly (Kitchen et al., 2005). By setting similar sites in the field as one management zone and in the Marudori method as the irrigation section it is possible to adopt a management method to further reduce in-field variation.

Former researchers used soil (Frogbrook and Oliver, 2007; Li et al., 2007) and yield (Jaynes et al., 2005a; Tagarakis et al., 2013; Vrindts et al., 2005) as indicators of identifying management zones. However, general-purpose indicators for examining management zones have not been obtained, so it is necessary to consider each crop or field. In this research, we focus on soil and yields used in these studies as indicators. Many of the preceding research cases also existed in citrus (Molin and de Castro, 2008; Zaman and Schumann, 2006). Many of them are for large and flat fields, and management zones with elevation and inclination as variables is assumed to be about 1.5 ° inclined (Fridgen et al., 2004). There are few cases of application to a relatively small scale sloping field as assumed in Marudori method.

In addition, in recent years, numerous rapid analysis methods for soil have been proposed (Adamchuk et al. 2004; Kuang et al. 2012), and portable soil sensors that can be used even on small scale gradient fields have been developed (Bogena et al., 2007; Ji et al., 2016). By conducting surveys with these sensors before the introduction of the Marudori method, there is a possibility to propose management zones that are in line with the actual conditions of each field. Therefore, in this study, we focused on the citrus fruit field using Marudori method, and aimed to examine suitability of these indices by discriminating irrigation sections with yields and soil components as indices in the sloping field.

Methods

Test field

The experiment was conducted in a 1200 m² citrus slope field on Iwagi Island of 8.95 km² area, Ehime prefecture, which belongs to the southwest region of Japan. The test was conducted in December 13, 2013, just after harvesting. Eighty nine citrus trees of 'Harehime' variety were planted in the test field. The field had 10 degrees of slope, the elevation difference was 5.9 m. This field used row irrigation system based on elevation. The field divided into 5 zones by irrigation strategies.

Data collection and soil sampling

A soil moisture / temperature / EC sensor (GS 3, Decagon) was inserted in the direction perpendicular to the excavation surface at the position of the soil surface, depth of 20 cm and depth of 40 cm to calculate the volumetric water content (VMC), soil temperature and electric conductivity (EC) was recorded. Hereinafter, VMC and EC at each depth are described as VMC₀, VMC₂₀, VMC₄₀, EC₀, EC₂₀, and EC₄₀. In this study, the yields of each tree from 2010 to 2013 (yield₂₀₁₀, yield₂₀₁₁, yield₂₀₁₂, yield₂₀₁₃) were used for analysis. Measurement by the portable soil sensing system is a total of 51 points, one for each tree, totaling 46 points, and 5 points from working road of the field. Since this field is located in a steep slope, the yield due to slope and the influence on soil are predicted. Therefore, positional information of 89 fruit trees in the test field was measured using RTK-GNSS. The positioning position was set to 1 m in the north direction from the trunk considering the root of the tree and the position of the irrigation tube

Cluster analysis

Cluster analysis was carried out using elevation, soil VMC, EC, elevation, yield and combination of all soil parameters and yield (soil + yield) as variables for reviewing the management zone. From the previous research, we used fuzzy c-means method. We used R 3.3.1 for analysis software (R Core Team, 2015), normalization was performed. We used fuzzy parameter $m = 1.5$ (Odeh et al., 1992). The yield data was analyzed except for the data of 34 and 42 of the fruit tree, which were missing. Since it is necessary to set the number of clusters beforehand at the time of cluster analysis, we set the number of clusters by using fuzziness performance index (FPI) and normalized classification entropy (NCE) as indices (Bezdek, 1981; Odeh et al., 1992).

Results

From each FPI and NCE, the minimum number of clusters to minimize each indicator was selected. Therefore, we choose 2 groups (soil + yield), 3 groups (VMC₀, VMC₂₀, VMC₄₀, EC₀, EC₂₀ and elevation), 4 groups (EC₄₀) 5 groups (yield).

Figure 1 shows the diagrams classified for each group obtained by cluster analysis. X and Y in figure 1 are described by plane rectangular coordinate system. As to the result of cluster analysis of soil, it is classified as high elevation, low elevation, high elevation, outer alley, in the middle of the field for VMC₄₀, high and low elevations in VMC₂₀ in the west side of the field, outer edge, high elevation in VMC₀ it was. In EC₀, it was classifiable into high elevation, low elevation, outer edge, EC₂₀ in outer edge and center row, high elevation, EC₄₀ in high elevation and in north and south direction including outer edge. Regarding the yield, it was classified into 5 groups, two in the upper part of the field, in the middle part of the field, in the lower part of the field and in the outer part. Regarding elevation, it was classified into three groups, upper part of the field, middle part of the field, and lower part of the field.

Since rowing irrigation is carried out in this field, it was confirmed by Fisher test whether row irrigation and the groups presented in this study are related. As a result, VMC 20, VMC 40, yield was shown to be independent at a significance level of 5%.

Figure 1. Results of cluster analysis on each layer of VMC and EC, elevation, yield and soil + yield.

Based on yield as indicator, this field can be divided into 5 groups. As a characteristic of each group, Group 1 located in the middle of the field was stably high yield, Group 2 was low yield only of yield₂₀₁₁, high yield in other fields, group 3 in the upper part of the field was high yield only in yield₂₀₁₃, in group 4 in the lower part of the field, high yields of yield₂₀₁₀ and yield₂₀₁₂, strong biennial results with low yields of yield₂₀₁₁ and yield₂₀₁₃, and group 5 in the upper part of the field were stably low yield. The high yield of the outer edge in yield groups 1 and 2 is attributed to edge effects (Hadjichristodoulou, 1993).

In VMC, water content was low for group 3 in VMC₀, high elevation and low elevation region, group 2 in VMC₂₀, and group 3 in VMC₄₀. In EC, values of Group 2, EC₂₀ and EC₄₀ of EC₀ located at the center to the bottom of the field are low, Groups 3 of EC₀ and EC₂₀ located at the upper part of the field and Groups 2 and 4 of EC₄₀ tend to be higher It was done.

In group 3 in VMC₂₀, group 5 in yield and group 5 in yield, the tendency of cluster analysis results to agree was noticeable. Group 3 of VMC₂₀ is a relatively high value group and yield group 5 is a relatively low value group. These trends agreed with the trend of the correlation coefficient, and similar trends were obtained even though VMC₀ and VMC₄₀ were not significant in the Fisher test.

In addition, although irrigation and fertilization are performed for each row in this field, the relevance between these and the cluster analysis results of VMC₂₀, VMC₄₀ and yield was confirmed. From these results, it was confirmed the influence on the yield by simultaneous fertilization of row type irrigation. However, the yield of each row was mixed in each group, so VMC and EC affected by irrigation could not explain this trend.

Discussion

Regarding the relationship between elevation and yield, it has been reported that there is a negative correlation in citrus (Mann et al., 2010). Similar trends have been observed except citrus (Tagarakis et al., 2013; Terra et al., 2006). However, this trend could not be observed in this test, and it was almost uncorrelated. Therefore, it is considered that in this field the influence on the yield by the row-type irrigation is larger than the influence by the elevation. Based on the above, variability in yield within the field due to simultaneous fertilization of row-type irrigation was observed in this field, indicating the possibility of being affected by the water retentivity of the soil other than the effect of fertilization, and only in the row-type irrigation, It was also suggested that there is a possibility that it cannot be made uniform yield.

Conclusion

Elevation, yield and soil VMC, EC in the 3 layer were classified by fuzzy c-means cluster analysis. VMC was 3, EC was 3 and 4, yield was 5, elevation was 3, soil + yield divided into 2 groups. The classified groups clearly showed the influence of cultivation of each variable. Comparing the row irrigation with the results of cluster analysis, it was observed that the groups in some variables after classification were affected by irrigation columns. At the same time, multiple groups were mixed in the same irrigation line. Therefore, it is suggested that the existing row-type irrigation may not be able to correct variability in field yield.

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